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Double Slit Quantum Superposition Computer

All the gates like OR, NOR, AND etc can be built with requencey of quantum double slit and superposition in a double slit experiment. And the advantage of such a computer is the CPU works at light speed in room temperature which is faster computational power than traditional quantum computers and are more stable. Light can split into multiple paths in a multiple path problem statement faster than electrons or qbits spin.

Founder and CEO SIU
Sanat Mohanty